

This contains the R code and the data required to run the code used for all data analysis in the manuscript titled:

" Sources of nitrous oxide emissions from agriculturally managed peatlands" by:

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an article accepted for publication in: Global Change Biology.

The data and code follow the structure of below:

The original data (including the details e.g., data source, unit of each parameter) were included in **excel file** namely, Table S1, Table S2, Table S3 and Table S6.

Table S1, Table S2, Table S3 and Table S6

The converted data (details of the conversion could be found in Material and method section 2.2.1 Selection of variables), which were used to set up the model and predict N₂O emissions were included in **.csv** file, namely Soil_N2O_dataset.csv and Soil_dataset.csv.

Soil N2O_dataset.csv and Soil_dataset.csv

The simulated results which were used for the figures in the paper were included in **.csv** file, namely fig2.1.csv, fig2.2.csv, fig2.3.csv, fig2.4.csv, fig3.csv, fig4.csv (files 7 – 12). Details calculation could be found in the Material and methos section 2.3 – 2.5.

fig2.1.csv, fig2.2.csv, fig2.3.csv, fig2.4.csv, fig3.csv, fig4.csv

The R code for setting up the model and predicting N₂O emissions and the R code for graphing each figure were include in. R file, namely modelsetup&predict.R, fig1.R, fig2.R, fig3.R and fig4.R.

modelsetup&predict.R, fig1.R, fig2.R, fig3.R and fig4.R

And the details e.g., the units for each column, and the name of each csv file were included in the Units.xlsx.

Units.xlsx